

TOOLS4CAP ACADEMY

MODULE I: INVENTORY OF METHODS AND TOOLS

17 January 2024

The first [Tools4CAP](#) (Innovative Toolbox empowering effective CAP governance towards EU ambitions) [Academy](#) module took place on 17 January 2024. The event gathered over 50 attendees from different backgrounds.

Tools4CAP's Academy aims to provide a framework for capacity building and peer-learning to develop an attractive and tailored training programme to meet the end users' needs. It wants to promote [meaningful engagement](#) of stakeholders that may benefit from this project. **This first module aims to:** (i) present the [inventory of methods and tools](#) used for the design and monitoring of Common Agricultural Policy Strategic Plans (CSPs) and the related [deliverable 1.1](#); (ii) discuss the usefulness and added value of the Inventory and (iii) enhance the exchange and learning.

During that training session, three presentations were made by [Ecorys](#) as project coordinator and [AEIDL](#) as Academy coordinator.

- Presentation of the project and its usefulness for the improvement of the design and monitoring of the national CSPs.
- Explanation of the objectives, activities and the development of the Academy.
- Feature the inventory of existing methods and tools around four categories: (1) stakeholders needs assessment tools; (2) policy choices supporting tools; (3) policy analysis tools for evidence-based decisions and (4) monitoring and data collection tools.

The session included participatory working groups focusing on the four tool categories. In each group, participants delved into the methodology, purpose and practical application of the tools. In addition, the inventoried tools were discussed and some of them were explored in more detail. Central to these discussions were two pivotal questions related to usefulness and application challenges of the tools.

Facilitated by Blanca Casares and Janne Sinerma from AEIDL, the Academy session concluded with outlined next steps. Meeting materials and the report summarising the key discussions will be made available on the [event page](#) and [YouTube channel](#). Additionally, this Highlights report will be translated into 16 EU languages covered by the consortium.

ORGANISER:

17 JANUARY 2024

ONLINE

50 PARTICIPANTS

EU institutions, national and regional public authorities, researchers, farmers, innovators, and other stakeholders relevant to the agricultural sector

22 COUNTRIES

PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

If you see this icon, click to see the presentation

If you see this icon, click to see the video

ACADEMY SESSIONS

The Tools4CAP project

Daniele Bertolozzi

Tools4CAP project's coordination, agricultural policy researcher and consultant (Ecorys)

Daniele Bertolozzi (Ecorys) introduced the [Tools4CAP](#) project, a Coordination and Support Action under Horizon Europe (2023-2026). Coordinated by [Ecorys](#), the project brings together 20 [partner organisations](#) with the aim of supporting the design and monitoring of current national CSPs and laying the groundwork for the preparation of post-2027 Strategic Plans.

Daniele outlined the project's approach for the upcoming years, highlighting the **expected outcomes**, which include:

- Development of a [conceptual framework](#) to establish a robust understanding of the New Delivery Model.
- Creation of a comprehensive [inventory](#) of methods and tools used across the 27 Member States.
- Formulation of methodological guidelines on innovative solutions and a handbook of good practices.
- Establishment of a Replication Lab to demonstrate the use of innovative methods and tools in 10 Member States through [case studies](#).
- Creation of a Capacity Building Hub aimed at assisting end users in reinforcing their capacity to use innovative solutions and good practices.

Conceptualisation and needs assessment for **understanding of the New Delivery Model**

Methodological guidelines for the implementation of innovative methods and tools

A Replication Lab to showcase the operational capacity to novel solutions of Member States through **10 case studies**

Tools4CAP key outcomes

Tools4CAP foresees the [active participation](#) from external stakeholders and the use of project' results. The project provides the possibility to get involved in different activities: focus groups, interviews, surveys, training sessions and dissemination activities. The [consent form](#) is available at the website.

GET INVOLVED
and take part in the
activities of Tools4CAP

Tools4CAP Capacity Building Hub: the Academy

Blanca Casares

Policy expert and project manager (AEIDL)

Blanca Casares (AEIDL), introduced the [Tools4CAP Academy](#), coordinated by [AEIDL](#) in close collaboration with other project partners. She started by giving an overview of who are the **main beneficiaries** of the project and the Academy. It includes:

- End users: policy-makers (EU, national and regional) and governance bodies.
- Universities, researchers and young scientists.
- Innovators and developers.
- Farmers, producers and producers' associations.
- Other stakeholders relevant to agricultural and rural development.

Blanca continued by explaining the Capacity Building Hub and its aim to help end-users **reinforce their capacity** to use innovative tools in the design and monitoring of CSPs. The Hub is made up of:

- The [Stakeholder Engagement Platform](#) which aims to facilitate bottom-up conversations and foster inclusive discussions. In total, 32 national multi-stakeholder focus groups will be organised across 16 countries covered by the consortium. It will be complemented with an [EU Focus Group](#).

Tools4CAP beneficiaries

- The [Academy](#) which provides a framework for capacity building and peer-learning in order to develop an attractive and tailored training programme composed of 10 modules to meet the end-users' needs. The results will be consolidated into a Capacity Building Toolkit, which will be translated into 16 EU languages.

Blanca then focused her presentation on giving more detail on the training content of the Academy's modules. In the coming months the topics for the **following modules** will be further defined and will cover: (i) the identification of tools, methodological guidelines and technical protocols on data integration; (ii) showcase of case studies; and (iii) the project's Handbook of good practices in cases studies. Also ad hoc trainings will tackle specific end users needs. Project's results will be integrated into a Capacity Building Toolkit.

In addition, Blanca explained other **additional activities of the Academy**, such as collecting experts' insights through interviews or blog articles, establishing joint actions with other projects or networks. She also introduced a dedicated section on the project's website: [practical information for CSP](#). It includes relevant documents, from the legal framework, to the approved national CSPs, and key sources for implementation, evaluation and innovation.

The information and materials of the modules will be available in the [specific section](#) of the website, at the event page and the [YouTube channel](#).

Inventory of methods and tools used by Member States

Joshua Wilson

Tools4CAP project's coordination. Consultant (Ecorys)

Joshua Wilson (Ecorys) provided an **in-depth overview of the Inventory** of existing methods and tools, which is one of the first results of Tools4CAP. He presented the **four methodological areas** in which methods and tools are classified:

- **Stakeholders needs assessment tools:** tools based on qualitative methodologies, including but not limited to participatory approaches. It includes 28 tools.
- **Monitoring and data collection tools:** tools that collect and make available (but do not interpret) the necessary information and data for the performance review of the CAP Strategic Plan, and to inform policy analyses and policy choices. It includes 27 tools.
- **Policy analysis tools for evidence-based decisions:** tools that generate (scientific or empirical) evidence through the analysis of policies, either ex-ante or ex-post, to inform decision-making, hence underpinning evidence-based policymaking. It includes 10 tools.
- **Policy choices supporting tools:** tools with logic-based methodologies that facilitate decision-making and are particularly useful when dealing with complex systems. It includes 10 tools.

Tools4CAP Inventory: Category Complementarity

So far of **data collection to build the existing Inventory** includes: (1) desk research, (2) 121 semi-structured interviews in 25 EU Member States and (3) the inputs of the 16 focus group at Member State level and the EU Focus Group.

The Inventory **includes a more detailed filtering system by CAP Strategic Plan relevant tasks:** **design** (socio-economic context analysis, SWOT analysis, needs assessment, intervention setting, target setting, financial allocation, ex-ante analysis and Strategic Environmental

Assessment and stakeholders consultations) **and monitoring** (beneficiaries' compliance, performance review and evaluation).

Work on the inventory will continue during the project, and **two updates are expected**, one in January 2025 and another in December 2026. Recently, a new feature has been added to the online inventory, allowing users to **provide feedback** on individual tools or on the Inventory as a whole.

GETTING INSIGHTS FROM PARTICIPANTS: RESULTS OF WORKING GROUPS

At the end of the training session participants were divided in working groups focusing on the four tool categories. In each group, participants delved into the methodology, purpose and practical application of the tools, along with their sub-categories. In addition, the inventoried tools were discussed and some of them were explored in more detail:

Group 1 spoke about two examples of farm level modelling tools used in Slovenia ([SiTFarm tool -Slovenian Typical Farm Model Tool](#)) and The Netherlands [Eco-Scheme Farm Simulation Tool](#) for the design of the current CSPs. The group discussed that although these are tools are very tailored to Member State specificities, from the technical point of view, they could easily be replicated.

In the case of the Slovenian tool, presented by Emil Erjavec (University of Ljubljana), the most important factors for replicability are the availability of data and the technical capacity of the ministry or the research institutes assisting the ministry. In the case of the Dutch tool, presented by Roel Jongeneel (Wageningen University) the group learned that it was not only developed for the design of the CSP, but was also used to support farmers in deciding on the use of eco-schemes.

Group 2 conversed about two examples of tools used for compliance monitoring in Portugal ([iSIP – Online Parcel Identification System](#)) and France [Dataplan Tool](#). The Portuguese tool is used to update field information collection, improve farmers' interactivity, and provide legal

backing, such as for eco-schemes. It includes information on legal constraints, agri-environmental measures, and eco-schemes, as well as relevant information for rural property management. The French tool is conceived as an interface between regional and national authorities that streamlines collaborative work for constructing the framework of reference for the French CSP, enabling data collection and sharing.

Group 3 discussed about two examples of tools used in the CSP design phase in Germany for stakeholder consultations and SWOT analysis ([World Café](#)) presented by Carla Wember (IfLS) and in Italy for needs assessment [Constrained Cumulative Voting](#) presented by Christian Schingo (ABACO).

Central to these discussions were two pivotal questions, driving the narrative of the session:

- To what extent are the inventoried tools useful for the users' needs?
- What are the main challenges and limitations in the use of the tools?

In closing the event Blanca Casares (AEIDL) thanked the audience and reminded recordings, presentations and this Highlights report will be available in the coming days on the [event page](#) and the [YouTube channel](#). This Highlights report will be soon translated into 16 EU languages covered by the consortium.

Academy module I: group reflections

www.tools4cap.eu

